

Supplemental Material

Novel pressure wave separation analysis for cardiovascular function assessment highlights major role of aortic root

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S1 Subject characteristics

S1.1 Characteristics of the hypertensive group

Characteristics	Mean±SD or n
Age, yr	46.2±17.1
Sex, male, %	53
BMI, kg/m ²	26.9±4.4
Drug therapy	
ACEI, %	15
ARB, %	8
β-Blocker, %	12
Calcium channel blocker, %	23
Diuretic, %	7
α-Blocker, %	6
Flow and pressure waveform	
HR, bpm	65.4±17.5
pSBP, mmHg	138.2±26.2
DBP, mmHg	82.8±21.2
cSBP, mmHg	129.5±27.5
cPP, mmHg	47.0±13.7
AP, mmHg	4.0±16.2
AIx, %	6.7±2.6
PWV, m/s	5.2±2.4
Umax, m/s	1.1±0.4

Table S1: Detailed characteristics of the hypertensive group. ACEI, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor; AIx, augmentation index; AP, augmentation pressure; ARB, angiotensin receptor blocker; BMI, body mass index; cPP, central pulse pressure; cSBP, central systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; HR, heart rate; pSBP, peripheral systolic blood pressure; PWV, pulse wave velocity; and Umax maximum flow velocity. Results are presented as mean±SD or as a percentage. Table adapted from [1].

S1.2 Characteristics of the normotensive group

Dose	HR (bpm)	DBP (mmHg)	P1 (mmHg)	P2 (mmHg)	PWV (m/s)	Umax (m/s)
Dobutamine (µg/kg/min)						
baseline	64.7±3.5	65.4±3.1	36.8±3.7	32.5±3.0	4.1±0.4	1.16±0.07
2.5	66.7±4.5	64.7±2.8	43.7±3.2	38.0±2.3	4.5±0.4	1.32±0.05
5	69.0±4.7	66.8±2.3	51.3±3.8	41.4±2.5	5.1±0.4	1.37±0.04
7.5	73.0±5.2	66.8±2.0	59.0±3.4	47.2±3.2	5.6±0.3	1.42±0.04
P value	0.024	0.58	<0.001	0.002	0.003	0.007
Norepinephrine (ng/kg/min)						
Baseline	60.9±3.2	66.2±3.1	35.3±1.7	33.0±3.0	4.4±0.3	1.14±0.03
12.5	56.5±3.2	71.1±3.0	36.5±2.0	35.8±2.3	4.7±0.4	1.15±0.04
25	54.3±3.1	74.2±3.0	33.1±1.4	37.3±2.7	4.7±0.3	1.07±0.05
50	52.3±2.9	78.7±2.9	36.8±2.8	43.7±4.3	5.6±0.6	1.07±0.06
P value	<0.001	<0.001	0.25	0.001	0.11	0.24
Phentolamine (µg/min)*						
Baseline	61.9±1.7	75.7±3.0	30.4±1.8	31.8±3.1	4.4±0.4	1.03±0.04
25	61.3±2.4	72.2±3.5	32.1±3.0	34.0±3.5	4.5±0.4	1.11±0.04
50	62.8±2.7	71.0±4.1	32.8±2.0	32.5±2.8	4.1±0.3	1.22±0.05
100	62.6±2.3	70.2±3.6	36.1±3.6	33.7±4.1	4.8±0.4	1.16±0.07
P value	0.39	0.021	0.13	0.42	0.41	0.098
Nitroglycerine (µg/min)						
Baseline	63.4±2.7	69.4±3.4	36.6±3.0	36.0±3.9	5.2±0.6	1.09±0.06
3	59.8±2.8	64.9±3.3	34.8±2.2	32.4±4.3	4.8±0.3	1.10±0.04
10	61.2±2.5	65.0±3.3	35.1±2.4	30.4±4.2	5.1±0.5	1.08±0.05
30	62.1±2.5	62.5±3.9	35.8±2.7	29.6±4.9	5.2±0.4	1.07±0.03
P value	0.26	0.018	0.70	0.033	0.63	0.79

Table S2: Detailed characteristics of the normotensive group. HR, heart rate; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; P1, height above DBP of the shoulder of aortic pressure; P2, height above DBP of the second systolic shoulder of aortic pressure; PWV, pulse wave velocity; Umax, maximum flow velocity. *With preceding boluses of 1, 2 and 4 mg for infusions of 25, 50 and 100 µg/min respectively.

S2 Aortic re-reflection pressure (P_{Ao}) and peripheral reflections pressure (P_{per})

Section 2.6.3.5 shows that the forward-travelling component, $P_{cc,f}(t)$, of the pressure generated by LV contraction within a cardiac cycle, $P_{cc}(t)$, can be expressed as $P_{cc,f} = P_{wh} + P_{Ao}$, where $P_{wh}(t) = Z_c \cdot Q$ is the water hammer pressure as defined by Parker *et al.* [2] and $P_{Ao}(t)$ is the aortic re-reflections pressure component. By applying the method of characteristics [3] to $P_{cc}(t)$ and $Q(t)$ we can show that P_{Ao} has the same magnitude as the peripheral reflections pressure component, $P_{per}(t)$. According to this method, P_{cc} can be separated into forward, $P_{cc,f}(t)$, and backward, $P_{cc,b}(t)$, travelling components by introducing the linear forward and backward Riemann variables, $W_{f,b}(t) = Q \pm \frac{P_{cc}}{Z_c}$ [4]. In the forward-travelling direction we have

$$P_{cc,f} = Z_c \frac{W_f}{2}, \quad (1)$$

$$W_f = Q + \frac{P_{cc}}{Z_c}. \quad (2)$$

Substitution of W_f into $P_{cc,f}$ yields

$$P_{cc,f} = \frac{1}{2}[P_{cc} + Z_c Q]. \quad (3)$$

Subtraction of $P_{wh} = Z_c \cdot Q$ from Eq. (3) leads to

$$P_{cc,f} - P_{wh} = \frac{1}{2}[P_{cc} - Z_c Q]. \quad (4)$$

Similarly, in the backward-traveling direction we have

$$P_{cc,b} = -Z_c \frac{W_b}{2}, \quad (5)$$

$$W_b = Q - \frac{P_{cc}}{Z_c}, \quad (6)$$

which combine to produce

$$P_{cc,b} = \frac{1}{2}[P_{cc} - Z_c Q]. \quad (7)$$

As described in Section 2.6.3.4, $P_{cc,b}$ is the peripheral reflections pressure made up of all peripheral reflections originating downstream of the aortic root within the cardiac cycle being analyzed; *i.e.* $P_{cc,b} = P_{per}$. As a result, combining Eqs. (4) and (7) leads to

$$P_{cc,f} = P_{wh} + P_{per} \quad (8)$$

and, hence,

$$P_{per} = P_{cc,f} - P_{wh}. \quad (9)$$

Comparing this equation with Eq. (9) in the main text we have that P_{A0} must have the same magnitude as P_{per} .

S3 Comparison between measured and approximated emission coefficients – Additional figures

Figure S3. Comparison between properties of the measured and approximated emission coefficient, $\gamma(t)$, calculated from Eqs. (2) and (4), respectively, in the main article. In the *in vivo* group, the time at which peak emission, γ_{peak} , was reached was similar in the measured and approximated $\gamma(t)$ ($R^2=0.69$, panel A), while the magnitudes of measured and approximated γ_{peak} in the *in silico* group were also highly correlated ($R^2=0.96$, panel B).

S4 Suppression of peripheral wave reflections – Additional figures

In silico baseline model for a healthy 25 y.o. subject

In silico baseline model for a healthy 35 y.o. subject

In silico baseline model for a healthy 45 y.o. subject

In silico baseline model for a healthy 55 y.o. subject

In silico baseline model for a healthy 65 y.o. subject

Figures S4. Effect of peripheral reflections on central pressure components and emission coefficient $\gamma(t)$ for the 25, 35, 45, 55 and 65 y.o. baseline subjects of the *in silico* group, with the same format as Fig. 5 showing the results for the 75 y.o. baseline subject.

Reference

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